

24GHz TSPC Frequency Divider for CMOS Application

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ABSTRACT

A 24GHz frequency divider is designed with 0.13 μ m CMOS technology and integrate with 24GHz phase lock loop (PLL) circuit. The TSPC circuits have a small area occupation and extremely low power consumption of 0.41mW for 24GHz frequency divider. 24GHz TSPC divider is designed with 5 stages of TSPC divider. The first stage of 24GHz TSPC divider is divide-by-fifteen (/15). The later four stages of 24GHz TSPC divider are designed with divide-by-two (/2) digital divider. To achieve the divided frequency of 100MHz which further can compare with the reference frequency of PLL, the 24GHz frequency divider has divider ratio of 240.

I. INTRODUCTION

An increasing demand of high performance consumer electronics and wireless communication requires low power, low cost and high frequency electronics. Due to the enhancement in design, performance and the decrease in size, low power consumption and high speed are the most difficult challenges that have to be addressed. Frequency divider circuit solve these issues and keep balance between these two requests. There are a variety of different Frequency divider schemes according to different types of logic used to design a divider. Well known is the two phase non overlapping clock [1]. In CMOS this principle expands into pseudo two phase clocking, actually using four clock phases [2]. Therefore it needs a bigger chip area for clock lines. These circuits

are very sensitive to clock races due to skew between clock phases. NORA circuit uses the two phase clocking scheme and removes race problem caused by clock skew [3]. NORA circuit technique does not operate on higher gigahertz input frequencies. The Current Mode Logic (CML) and injection locked frequency divider (ILFD) is mainly used to achieve a high operating frequency. However CML and ILFD frequency divider schemes dissipates high power and requires larger chip area. While TSPC technology incorporates small chip area, high speed and low power consumption, but cannot reach the speed of CML and ILFD frequency divider. The structure of 24GHz TSPC divider is manufactured in 0.13 μ m CMOS technology. Measurement and simulation results are presented.

II. Circuit DESIGN

TSPC circuit technique need of only one clock signal for operation. Therefore, no clock skew exists except for clock delay problems. Furthermore in TSPC circuit higher clock frequencies can be reached at low power consumption. TSPC circuit principle is based on the charging and evaluating stages. The general structure and clock timing of the conventional TSPC circuit scheme is shown in figure 1. When the clock signal is low, the nodes N1, N2, N3 are simultaneously charged to VDD and node N4 is charged to GND. DUE to this precharging the speed of the TSPC structure is increases. The previous stage evaluation data is held at node OUTPUT. When the clock is high the N1, N2, N3 and the output nodes changes, due to the

N transistor logic blocks. For P transistor logic blocks, the evaluation takes place with falling clock edges and charging takes place with rising clock edges.

Fig. 1. General structure with N-transistor logic and clock timing of the true single phase clock technique

There are several basic schemes that are used to create TSPC circuit [6]. The different blocks, n dynamic block, p dynamic block, n latch block and p latch block of complementary static logic gates are shown, in figure 2.

III. RESULTS

The 24GHz TSPC frequency divider was designed in a 0.13 μ m CMOS technology and integrate with 24GHz phase lock loop (PLL) circuit. 24GHz TSPC frequency divider circuit has five cascaded TSPC circuits, four cascaded TSPC stages of /2 and one TSPC stages of /15. At a supply voltage of 0.9V, a simulated power consumption is 0.41mW. The input waveform of 24GHz and output waveform, first stage of TSPC frequency divider (/15), of 1.6GHz and output waveform, four cascaded TSPC stages (/2), 800MHz, 400MHz, 200MHz, 100MHz are respectively in figure 3.

Fig. 2. Basic blocks of TSPC circuit technique: a) n-dynamic block, b) p-dynamic block, c) n-latch, d) p-latch

Fig. 3 shows the input and output waveforms for the first stage of TSPC frequency divider

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IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, the 24GHz TSPC frequency divider structure has been investigated and designed by using 0.13 μ m CMOS technology. Advanced Design System (ADS) is used to produce simulation results. The maximum operating frequency of designed 24GHz TSPC frequency divider is 23GHz to 26GHz. The power consumption at 24GHz at supply voltage of 0.9V is 0.41mW.

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